

KGI4NFDI

Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for the German National Research Data Infrastructure

Services for creating, discovering, connecting, and using knowledge graphs for NFDI,
EOSC and beyond

Proposal for the Integration phase of a Basic Service in Base4NFDI

Submitted: January 28th 2026

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18331633>

1 General Information

- **Name of proposed Basic Service:** (in English):
Knowledge Graph Infrastructure for the German National Research Data Infrastructure
- **Acronym of the proposed Basic Service:** KGI4NFDI
- **Service "subtitle" explaining key functionality:**
Services for creating, discovering, connecting, and using knowledge graphs for NFDI, EOSC and beyond
- **Corresponding NFDI Section:** (Meta)data, Terminologies, Provenance
- **Lead institution:** ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences, Gleueler Strasse 60, 50931 Cologne
- **Name of lead institution principal investigator:** Prof. Dr. Konrad Förstner, foerstner@zbmed.de
- **Authors of the proposal:**
Lozana Rossenova, Renat Shigapov, Moritz Schubotz, Fidan Limani, Benjamin Zapilko, Muhammad Elhossary, Daniel Mietchen, Till Sauerwein, Konrad Förstner
- **Participating institutions:**

Principal Investigator	Institution, location	Contact E-mail	Member in [consortium] ¹	Funding requested [yes no]
Prof. Dr. Konrad Förstner	ZB MED – Information Centre for Life Sciences, Cologne	foerstner@zbmed.de	NFDI4Microbiota	yes
Dr. Lozana Rossenova	TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, Hannover	lozana.rossenova@tib.eu	NFDI4Culture	yes
Dr. Renat Shigapov	Mannheim University Library, Mannheim	renat.shigapov@uni-mannheim.de	BERD@NFDI	yes
Dr. Moritz Schubotz	FIZ Karlsruhe – Leibniz Institute for Information Infrastructure, Berlin	moritz.schubotz@fiz-karlsruhe.de	MaRDI	yes
Fidan Limani	ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics, Kiel	f.limani@zbw.eu	KonsortSWD	yes
Dr. Benjamin Zapilko	GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences, Mannheim	Benjamin.Zapilko@gesis.org	NFDI4DataScience	yes

Table 1: List of participating institutions

¹ Name one DFG consortium the institution is or has a route to become a member of and through which funds should be appropriated if this proposal is approved.

- **Initialisation Phase:** June 2024 - December 2025
- **Planned duration of the integration phase:** Two years
- **Statement on efforts required by consortia for integration of service**

KGI4NFDI aims to make the use, deployment, and maintenance of Knowledge Graphs (KGs) simple and scalable. The effort needed from consortia is flexible and tailored to their specific needs, ranging from minimal to more involved activities. Through structured incubator calls and consultancy office hours, we make deploying and configuring KGs a well-supported process. Depending on the starting point, targeted simple steps guide consortia to configure and contribute new or existing KGs to the central Hub and Registry, thereby unlocking multiple advantages of cross-institutional and cross-disciplinary interoperability and a seamless connection to global resources (including OpenAIRE, Wikidata, EOSC and more).

- **Summary of the proposal in English and German**

EN: The KGI4NFDI aims to support the creation, discovery, connection, and use of KGs within the NFDI ecosystem, EOSC, and beyond. This Basic Service builds upon the achievements of the Initialisation Phase and addresses the increasing demand for KG deployment, a central KG Hub, interoperability, and community engagement. In this context, an incubator program will enable projects to generate and maintain KGs supported by KGI4NFDI, facilitating decentralised KG instances based on standards and tried-and-tested approaches. Furthermore, Registry and Hub services are refined to provide a more user-friendly interface for querying across different KGs with improved semantic interoperability. Consultancy services will be expanded to actively engage the NFDI community in the creation and use of KGs through various initiatives, including workshops, webinars, and dedicated events. Our approach is expected to contribute significantly to the vision of “One NFDI” by promoting the standardisation practices that enhance data integration capabilities. We also align with prevalent international initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), creating a sustainable KG infrastructure. Feedback from the Initialisation phase offered valuable insights from the NFDI community, some aligning with the Initialisation Phase's scope and others thoughtfully incorporated into the proposal for the Integration Phase.

DE: Ziel von KGI4NFDI ist es, die Erstellung, Entdeckung, Verbindung und Nutzung von Wissensgraphen (Knowledge Graphs, KG) innerhalb des NFDI-Ökosystems, der EOSC und darüber hinaus zu unterstützen. Dieser Basisdienst baut auf den Resultaten der Initialisierungsphase auf und adressiert die steigende Nachfrage nach Bereitstellung von KGs, einem zentralen KG-Hub, Interoperabilität und dem Einbinden der Community. In einem Inkubatorprogramm werden Projekte in die Lage versetzt, KGs zu erstellen und zu pflegen, um dezentrale KG-Instanzen auf Basis von Standards und bewährten Ansätzen zu ermöglichen. Darüber hinaus werden Registry- und Hub-Dienste verbessert, um eine benutzerfreundliche Schnittstelle für die Abfrage verschiedener KGs mit semantischer Interoperabilität zu schaffen. Die

Beratungsdienste werden ausgeweitet, um die NFDI-Gemeinschaft durch Aktivitäten wie Workshops, Webinare und spezielle Veranstaltungen in die Erstellung und Nutzung von KGs einzubinden. Es wird erwartet, dass unser Ansatz durch die Förderung von Standards, die die Datenintegration verbessern, einen wichtigen Beitrag zur Vision von „One NFDI“ leistet. Wir sind auch im Austausch mit internationalen Initiativen wie der European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) und schaffen eine nachhaltige KG-Infrastruktur. Feedback aus der Initialisierungsphase lieferte wertvolle Erkenntnisse, von denen einige direkt adressiert und andere in den Antrag für die Integrationsphase aufgenommen wurden.

2 Summary of Initialisation Phase Results

2.1 Change in Background and Motivation since the start of the Initialisation Phase

The background and motivation for the KGI service has changed significantly since the start of the Initialisation Phase in two ways:

1. Following more in-depth research within NFDI communities, we have noticed that adoption trends for KGs are low due to a common perception that there are no easy solutions for deploying and hosting KGs for individual research projects.
2. The mainstream adoption of commercial and/or closed source LLM-driven services as knowledge discovery tools, despite ongoing issues with the accuracy of the results delivered by such tools.

At a first glance, these shifts in researcher behaviours might suggest that a service such as KGI is not meeting current user needs. However, we believe that supporting the integration phase of KGI is in fact more important now than ever. Integrating the existing KG solutions offered by the KGI consulting service with concrete infrastructure already available (via de.NBI - the German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure², see provided LoC) for concrete NFDI use cases (via incubator projects) will address point 1 above. Only once a critical mass of NFDI projects are actively using KGs can we begin to address point 2. An LLM-driven user interface offers many user experience advantages, including improved accessibility, but without the solid background of structured knowledge (in KGs) that the LLM-interface can access, results do not meet scientific standards and might contribute to bad (or worsening) scientific practices.

2.2 Results of the Initialisation Phase

The Initialisation Phase of KGI4NFDI delivered a central Hub and Registry to aggregate information on KGs contributed by NFDI consortia and communities. A comprehensive survey was

² <https://www.denbi.de/>

conducted to refine and optimize the KGI services. Consultancy services were established to support consortium members in creating their own KG solutions. Guidelines³ for creating, hosting, and using KGs were compiled and open-sourced. The monthly consultancy hours started in January 2025. Consultancy requests are received via the KGI4NFDI mailing list and documented. In addition, a range of queries have been developed as showcases. A harmonisation strategy has also been developed to ensure consistency across different consortia's ontologies. These accomplishments demonstrate the project's potential for fostering KG adoption and enhancing data integration capabilities. The questions about the need of KGs in NFDI raised by the Technical Expert Committee (TEC) have been answered, as several consortia and institutions have reported their interest and are in exchange with the KGI4NFDI project team to initiate the creation of KGs. The survey results also clearly document the need. The solutions provided by KGI4NFDI have been widely accepted as a technical unification and integration layer of NFDI.

Registry and Hub: Information about KGs maintained by the consortia was compiled and modelled using two ontologies: DCAT⁴ and NFDIcore⁵. We host the KG engines and SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language) endpoints that serve the generated datasets. Two engines were tested for this, Apache Jena Fuseki⁶ and QLever⁷, after which the latter was selected for its superior performance. A web interface for the SPARQL endpoint was developed to serve the KG Registry dataset and was published under subdomains^{8,9} of Base4NFDI. All development code is maintained in GitHub repositories^{10,11}, incorporating a CI/CD pipeline for automated deployment. Containerization using Docker is used to streamline deployment and ensure environmental consistency across different development stages. The Hub will be further developed as suggested by the TEC to offer overarching query solutions, making it one joint resource for all disciplines.

Consultancy: The guidelines for creating, using, and querying KGs were compiled and released under open CC-BY license via GitHub¹². The guidelines, deployed with GitHub Pages¹³, are openly accessible. The resources cover installation and configuration, data import and modelling, and querying the KGs using Apache Jena (Fuseki), Virtuoso, Wikibase, and QLever. Additionally, consultancy sessions started via e-mails in December 2024 and via Zoom in January 2025. The

³ <https://kgi4nfdi.github.io/Guidelines>

⁴ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

⁵ <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/>

⁶ <https://jena.apache.org/documentation/fuseki2/>

⁷ <https://qllever.dev/wikidata>

⁸ <https://kgi.services.base4nfdi.de>

⁹ <https://sparql.kgi.services.base4nfdi.de>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/base4nfdi/kgi4nfdi/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/KGI4NFDI>

¹² <https://github.com/KGI4NFDI/Guidelines>

¹³ <https://kgi4nfdi.github.io/Guidelines>

consultancy requests and sessions are documented and clearly show that NFDI communities need a service for outsourcing the deployment of KGs.

Interoperability Strategy: Investigations on existing frameworks and initiatives as well as a stakeholder analysis were conducted. As a result, interoperability dimensions specifically for the use cases of KG generation and KG access have been defined. Moreover, best practices and guidelines to facilitate metadata mapping, linking, and integration were developed and published¹⁴. Example queries for single KGs, but also for conducting federated queries are integrated into the Registry and aim to facilitate access and insight of the registered KGs.

2.2.1 Interim report on requirements for finalisation of the initialisation phase

This section covers only a few highlights - further information can be found in the full report.

a) Requirements analysis (D1.4.1)

Due: 3 months after start date | Percent finished 100% | Status: **finished**

Overview of relevant outcomes: We have gathered feedback on different aspects of KG adoption and use across NFDI consortia, including potential support that KGI4NFDI could provide.

Deliverables and Milestones: Interviews with NFDI Consortias (reported in D1.4.1 Requirements analysis), D4.1 Survey of existing KG adoption practices in NFDI.

Outlook: Communication with the interested stakeholders will be continued.

b) Software evaluation (D1.4.2)

Due: 6 months after start date | Percent finished 100%: | Status: **finished**

Overview of relevant outcomes: The DCAT ontology was initially implemented, and additionally mappings to NFDIcore Ontology¹⁵ were later added for better alignment with the NFDI ecosystem and comprehensive attribute coverage. Migration from Apache Jena/Fuseki to Qlever was completed for better engine performance.

Deliverables and Milestones: D1.1 Registry of KGs in NFDI, D1.2 Platform for search and query across KGs.

Outlook: Performance, functionality, and usability will be further monitored.

c) Service design (D1.4.3)

Due: 6 months after start date | Percent finished 100% | Status: **finished**

Overview of relevant outcomes: The design for the KG Registry and the query service have been finalized and documented. Metadata for KGs was modelled and a submission form was

¹⁴ KGI4NFDI - Best practices and guidelines for metadata mapping, linking, and integration <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15780729>

¹⁵ <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/>

implemented in Github for public access. KG addition is automated via supervised pipeline.

Deliverables and Milestones: D1.1 Registry of KGs in NFDI, D1.2 Platform for search and query across KGs, Task: Documentation template setup, Task: Create KG submission form on GitHub, specification of interoperability dimensions.

Outlook: The submission form is continuously adapted according to the community needs.

d) Service prototype (D1.4.4)

Due: 12 months after start date | Percent finished 100% | Status: **finished**

Overview of relevant outcomes: Registry of KG prototype implemented; Consultancy service running; Report analysing existing interoperability frameworks, specified interoperability dimensions, and best practices; Guidelines for metadata mapping, linking, integration; Report on engagement towards interoperability issues with national and international initiatives.

Deliverables and Milestones: D1.1 Registry of KGs in NFDI, D1.2 Platform for search and query across KGs, D2.2 Consultancy service, D3.1 Strategy for metadata mapping, linking, and integration, D3.2 Strategy for interoperability with national and international KG initiatives, D4.2 Showcases.

Outlook: Upscaling and advancing the prototype with enhanced features during Integration Phase.

e) Service piloting and user testing (D1.4.5)

Due: 12 months after start date | Percent finished 100% | Status: **finished**

Overview of relevant outcomes: Registry of KGs in NFDI is openly deployed and tested by partner institutions. Guidelines for creating and hosting KGs using four KG software engines (Wikibase, Apache Jena, Virtuoso, and QLever) have been compiled, open-sourced on GitHub, and openly deployed on GitHub Pages. Users can provide their feedback via GitHub issues.

Deliverables and Milestones: D1.1 Registry of KGs in NFDI, D1.2 Platform for search and query across KGs, D2.1 Guidelines for creating and hosting KGs, M2.1 Guidelines available online, Task: Wikibase deployment guidelines, Task: Apache Jena deployment guidelines, Task: Virtuoso deployment guidelines, Task: QLever deployment guidelines.

Outlook: Continuous collection of user feedback on the Hub and Registry.

2.2.2 Other

Five User Personas with multiple User Stories have been created during multiple workshops. Participation at Base4NFDI User conference 2024 and 2025, Base4NFDI Services Roadshow, EOSC Symposium 2024 and CoRDI 2025.

2.3 Update on Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of the Basic Service

While the TLR of the underlying open-source software is high (8 - 9), the Registry and Hub are still under development, providing a TRL of 6.

3 Working Concept for the development of the Basic Service

The KGI4NFDI is designed to support creating, managing, using, discovering, and querying KGs within the NFDI ecosystem. This Basic Service builds upon the outcomes of the Initialization Phase and addresses the **growing need for deployment of KGs**, semantic interoperability, and community engagement. The integration phase will solidify the foundational components of KGI4NFDI while scaling its services to a broader audience. The development of the Basic Service is structured to balance technical advancements with community engagement. The focus is on achieving **interoperability across technical, semantic, and organizational** levels while fostering collaboration among NFDI consortia, research institutions, and international initiatives. By aligning with common standards, KGI4NFDI aims to **simplify KG adoption, enhance discoverability, and promote cross-disciplinary research**. During the integration phase, KGI4NFDI will provide consultancy, training, and open educational resources, engaging with the NFDI's 'Knowledge Graphs' working group and initiatives like EOSC, to **ensure global alignment**. With a clear focus on **scalability, sustainability, and openness**, the integration phase sets the stage for transitioning KGI4NFDI into the Ramping Up phase, where it will achieve its full potential as a central resource for the NFDI community and beyond. At the moment we do not intend to charge user fees after the funding of the service through Base4NFDI. Furthermore, we seek to become a core funded service by the NFDI. As the future funding, the overall organisational and technical architecture of NFDI is currently planned on several decision levels, we can currently not give specific solutions. The six partners are committed to continue the service after the funding due to a certain extent and due to the usage of the de.NBI cloud as deployment platform a long-term provision of the individually created knowledge graph systems is possible without significant dedicated resources.

3.1 Service Integration Concept

The integration of KGI4NFDI services with partner consortia will deliver **technical, semantic, and organizational interoperability** across the NFDI landscape. This approach ensures that KGI4NFDI serves as a **unifying infrastructure** aiming to: 1) **significantly increase adoption** of KGs through incubator and deployment projects; 2) **integrate new and existing** KGs from partner consortia (including but not limited to MaRDI, NFDI4Culture, and NFDI4Microbiota) into its **central**

KG Hub; 3) enhance **usability and accessibility** of the integrated services through implementation of LLM-based approaches to user interaction. These measures combined will enable efficient querying and retrieval of metadata across consortia following best practices and interoperability standards. Collaboration with Base Services, such as IAM4NFDI and TS4NFDI, will further enhance the value proposition of all services to their respective users, and future integrations are planned to include more Base Services as they become available. On an organizational level, all project partners are active members of various NFDI consortia, ensuring that the **integration strategy is aligned with the broader goals of the NFDI community**. Regular collaboration through workshops, working group meetings (e.g., the NFDI working group "Knowledge Graphs" in Section Metadata), and project-specific engagements, will strengthen these ties and foster a shared vision for KG adoption. Services and other outcomes developed within individual consortia that are relevant to this vision, e.g. Wikibase4Research¹⁶ and the NFDIcore Ontology, originally developed in the context of NFDI4Culture, will be tightly integrated into the architecture and service offerings of KGI. Additionally, to support partner consortia, KGI4NFDI will offer consultancy services and training sessions. Workshops and knowledge-sharing events, such as the NFDI Knowledge Graph Day and webinars, will promote the adoption of standards and demonstrate the benefits of interoperable KGs. Feedback mechanisms, including surveys and consultation sessions, will ensure continuous improvement and alignment with user needs.

The success of the integration phase will be measured using a set of key performance indicators (KPIs). **Technical KPIs** will include the number of deployed and integrated KGs, system uptime, and query response times, example queries accessible via the Hub, as well as integration of other Base services. **Community KPIs** will focus on the number of workshops conducted, participants engaged, consultancy requests resolved, and on the user study conducted with the KGI Hub and Registry. **Adoption KPIs** will measure the number of consortia and institutions involved in incubators and contributing to the central Hub and Registry.

KGI4NFDI remains committed to openness, with all software components using **open licenses** and outputs such as documentation, training materials, and datasets being **openly accessible**. KGI4NFDI complements existing **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Node** offerings by focusing on KGs as a foundational technology. Integration with EOSC standards and services will promote the reuse of KG data and align KGI4NFDI as a **valuable EOSC Node resource**. Additionally, collaboration with EOSC will enhance international interoperability and contribute to the global research data ecosystem. These efforts build on WP2 results - harmonized ontologies,

¹⁶ <https://gitlab.com/nfdi4culture/wikibase4research>

benchmark queries, and a query gallery - ensuring **semantic alignment and technical consistency** for integrating KGs across consortia and the EOSC framework.

3.2 Future Development and Ramp-up Outlook

The plan for the integration phase is to reach a service that fulfills the requirements for the ramping up phase. This includes that we aim to reach a **TRL of 7-8** based on a state-of-the-art technology stack that enables us **to reach TRL 9** eventually. Apart from the technical development, this requires also a concept for sustainable operation of the service. Here, we aim to build on established and reliable computational infrastructure provided by de.NBI. With our incubator activities, we plan to not only increase but also to strengthen our collaborations with other NFDI consortia (see WP3). With a special focus on KGs, we complement existing EOSC EU node services.

3.3 Risks and Challenges

Several potential risks were identified and measures to mitigate them planned:

Risk Description	Likelihood	Severity	Mitigation Strategy
Lack of adoption by the NFDI Community	medium	critical	Collect numerous LoCs of consortia willing to join as incubator projects; offer consultation and tailored workshops / webinars; work on optimising usability and accessibility.
Technical scalability	medium	moderate	Collaboration with de.NBI for compute infrastructure; using Qlever for better performance.
Parallel Development with similar Initiative	medium	minor	Participating in international working groups and forums and exchange with OpenAIRE and similar initiatives

Table 2: Risks and challenges

4 Support Actions from Base4NFDI / NFDI Sections, and Integrating NFDI Consortia / Efforts

Support from	Work package / Description of contribution	Contact person Basic Service
Base4NFDI; Section Common Infra.; Section Metadata	WP 1 “Hub and Registry” Support coordination with related Base Services, such as IAM4NFDI, TS4NFDI, PID4NFDI, etc.j	B. Zapilko, K. Förstner
Base4NFDI; Section Common Infra.; Section Metadata - WG “Ontology mapping and harmonization”	WP 2 “Interoperability” : Support interoperability and alignment with related Base Services and individual NFDI consortia, as well as relevant initiatives outside the NFDI.	M. Schubotz, F. Limani
Base4NFDI; Section	WP 3 “Incubators and Deployment” : Provide a broader	F. Limani,

Common Infra.; Section Metadata; KGI4NFDI Partner institutions	outreach to the interested NFDI consortia in adopting and/or extending the practices and services being developed in the KGI4NFDI. This also includes organizations that are not (yet) part of the NFDI.	R. Shigapov
Base4NFDI; Section Metadata - WG “Knowledge Graphs”	WP 4 “Community Engagement and Consultancy” : Support in promoting the role of and adoption of KGs and corresponding practices.	R. Shigapov, L. Rossenova
Base4NFDI; Section Metadata - WG “Knowledge Graphs”	WP 5 “Integration and collaboration with other Base Services” : Support the integration of Base services currently in their integration phase.	L. Rossenova, M. Schubotz

Table 3: Support needed from Base4NFDI / Service Stewards / Section

5 Work Programme

The following working programme was developed based on the experiences and the feedback gathered from our community survey conducted from December 5, 2024, to December 31, 2024¹⁷, as well in close exchange with the Base4NFDI team and other Base4NFDI services, especially TS4NFDI. We are committed to building an inclusive service and will proactively address accessibility throughout development, adhering to Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) guidelines and incorporating further accessibility best practices.

Figure 1: Overview of the KGI4NFDI working programme in the Integration Phase.

5.1 Overview of Work Packages

Work package	Deliverables (D) and milestones (M)	Responsible partner(s)	Related work packages
1. Hub and Registry	D1.1: Testing suite (Q4) D1.2: User study of Registry and Hub (Q5) D1.3: Advanced version of the Hub and Registry (Q6) M1.1: Central Knowledge Management Infrastructure (Q8)	GESIS (contributions: TIB, ZB MED)	4, 6
2. Interoperability	D2.1: Benchmark queries for assessing KG interoperability (Q1) D2.2: Ontology and License fields available in the Hub (Q3) D2.3: Final report on EOSCxNFDI KG interoperability (Q7) M2.1: Semantic Interoperability KPIs defined (Q2) M2.2: Gallery of actionable queries accessible (Q4) M2.3: First evaluation of interoperability measures released (Q6)	FIZ (contributions: ZBW)	3, 6

¹⁷ Report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717742>

	M2.4: Collection of EOSCxNFDI success stories released (Q8)		
3. Incubators and Deployment	D3.1: Incubator project guidelines published (Q1) D3.2: Deployment pipelines tested (Q3) D3.3: Deployment documentation published (Q4) D3.4: Reports for each incubator cycle (Q7) D3.5: Final report on outcomes and best practices (Q8) M3.1: First incubator cycle completed (Q4) M3.2: Second incubator cycle completed (Q5) M3.3: Third incubator cycle completed (Q6) M3.4: Fourth incubator cycle completed (Q8)	ZBW (contributions: ZB MED, UB Mannheim, GESIS)	2, 6
4. Community Engagement and Consultancy	D4.1: Strategy for community engagement and consultancy (Q1) D4.2: User-centred documentation and open educational resources published (D.Int.7) (Q4) D4.3: Knowledge graph events and trainings organised (D.Int.7) (Q5 with extensions to Q8) D4.4: Community impact report (Q8) M4.1: Launch of community engagement activities (Q2)	UB Mannheim (contribution: TIB, ZBW)	3, 6
5. Integration and collaboration with other Base Services	D5.1: Participation in Base4NFDI outreach events (D.Int.9) (Q1-8: throughout the project duration) D5.2: Report on integration results, use cases and best practices (D.Int.1) (Q8) M5.1: Integration with services currently in Integration Phase (Q2) M5.2: Integration with services currently in Initialisation Phase (Q5) M5.3: Integration with upcoming services (Q7)	TIB (contribution: FIZ, ZB MED)	2, 6
6. Coordination and Outreach	D6.1: Definition of KPIs (Q1) D6.2: Provision of service portfolio metadata (D.Int.4) (Q2) D6.3: Midterm-Report, including documentation of service maturity and sustainability (D.Int.2, D.Int.3) (Q4) D6.4: Self-assessments of software quality (D.Int.5) (Q4/Q8) D6.5: Documentation of usability (D.Int.6) (Q4/Q8) D6.6: Final report, including documentation of service maturity and sustainability (D.Int.2, D.Int.3) (Q8) M6.1: KPIs defined and collection implemented (Q2) M6.2: Short overview about the outcomes of the Integration phase and presentation in a section meeting (D.Int.8) (Q7) M6.3: Project phase conclusion (Q8)	ZB MED (contribution: all)	1, 2, 3, 4, 5

Table 4: Overall work programme with work packages, deliverables, milestones, and responsible partner

5.2 Detailed Work Programme

Work Packages, Tasks, Deliverables and Milestones	Base Service “Knowledge Graph Infrastructure”							
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8
WP1: Hub and Registry								
Deliverables				D1.1	D1.2	D1.3		
Milestones								M1.1
WP2: Interoperability								
Deliverables	D2.1		D2.2				D2.3	
Milestones		M2.1		M2.2		M2.3		M2.4
WP3: Incubators & Deployment								
Deliverables	D3.1		D3.2	D3.3			D3.4	D3.5

Work Packages, Tasks, Deliverables and Milestones	Base Service “Knowledge Graph Infrastructure”							
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8
Milestones				M3.1	M3.2	M3.3		M3.4
WP4: Community engagement and consultancy								
Deliverables	D4.1			D4.2	D4.3			D4.4
Milestones		M4.1						
WP5: Integration and collaboration with other Base Services								
Deliverables	D5.1							D5.2
Milestones		M5.1			M5.2		M5.3	
WP6: Coordination and Outreach								
Deliverables	D6.1	D6.2		D6.3,4,5				D6.4,5,6
Milestones		M6.1					M6.2	M6.3

Chart 1: Gantt chart with work packages (WPx), deliverables (Dx.y), and milestones (Mx.y).

5.2.1 WP1 - Hub and Registry (11 PMs GESIS, 2 PMs TIB, 4 PMs ZB MED)

The “Hub and Registry” Working Package aims to establish a central knowledge management infrastructure for the KGI4NFDI service, with two key components: the Hub and the Registry. The Registry, initiated during the Initialisation Phase, will be extended by incorporating new KGs registered by NFDI consortia or generated during the incubator projects. Reusing standard ontologies, including the NFDIcore Ontology, for representing the KGs within the Registry provides a robust foundation for knowledge sharing and discovery. The Hub, initially built during the Initialisation Phase, will be extended to provide **a centralized access point for querying and retrieving** information across different KGs registered in the Registry, including showcase queries. Both Hub and Registry will be further developed to shift them from a prototypical stage to a production system with a higher TRL. This includes the integration of standard software **testing routines** like unit testing, integration testing as well as functional tests. Dedicated **user and accessibility testing** activities with external stakeholders will form the basis for advancing the Hub and Registry. A **natural language interface** for querying KGs based on open Large Language Models (LLMs) which will be tested with explicit aim to further increase **accessibility**.

5.2.2 WP2 - Interoperability (13 PMs FIZ, 2 PMs ZBW)

The Interoperability Working Package is aimed at ensuring seamless interoperability - with an **initial focus on semantic interoperability** - at **two main levels**: between NFDI-related KGs (**NFDI level**) as well as between KGI4NFDI and other relevant initiatives and resources, both within and beyond NFDI. Alignment with Semantic Web standards and related protocols is crucial for both levels, as is legal and policy interoperability, particularly concerning licensing and data protection. In addition, semantic interoperability for the NFDI level rests on **alignment and normalisation of**

data models between and across NFDI KGs and associated tooling, particularly for data validation and integration. This includes attention to data types, data formats, value normalisation, consistency checks and community-specific adaptations. Related **tooling** concerns querying KGs and functionalities like import (e.g. from nanopublications or non-KG data sources), export (e.g. as nanopublications or subgraph dumps), format conversions (e.g. to and from tabular data), quality checks (e.g. schema compliance or logical coherence) or visualisations (e.g. for research or education). These technical measures will be combined with a harmonised approach to describing NFDI-related KGs and documenting their creation and use. Building on existing collaborations with national and international partners, the NFDI level interoperability efforts will be synchronised with infrastructure providers at the **EOSC level** and beyond, which requires exploring, documenting and handling additional technical and policy parameters. Partnering infrastructure providers for this WP include Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC), OpenAIRE and EOSC, the Wikimedia Foundation, among others.

5.2.3 WP3 - Incubators and Deployment (15 PMs ZBW, 11 PMs ZB MED, 8 PMs UB Mannheim, 6 PMs GESIS)

This Work Package is designed to provide a **structured pathway** for interested communities to adopt or expand KG practices. It also aims to encourage exploration of emerging technologies, innovative use cases, and illustrative showcases. Building on the successful experiences of other Base4NFDI services like IAM4NFDI and TS4NFDI, this WP will launch a **Call for Incubator Projects** and invite proposals from NFDI consortia or research communities interested in leveraging KGI-based services. The incubator approach involves projects working through a **series of focused sprints**, with each incubator cycle lasting approximately six months.

Figure 2: Workflow of the Incubator calls.

Working through the sprints, participants are expected to deliver a functional KG at the end of the cycle. Proposals submitted in response to the incubator calls will be evaluated by an Incubator Board. This board comprises experts in KG development, research infrastructure, and NFDI-related topics, ensuring thorough and informed review processes. A maximum of 10 selected

projects will foster collaboration in KG development within the NFDI community. Incubators will also be implemented in close collaboration with related Base4NFDI projects, especially TS4NFDI. KG deployment is the second component of this WP: not all communities have the necessary (deployment) infrastructure to put their KGs into production, and this component will enable the incubation cycle to generate a Minimum Viable Product (MVP). The provision of LLM-based natural language interface for querying those KGs (developed in WP1) will be explored. The German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI) has confirmed to provide infrastructure also for KGs of communities beyond the life sciences (see Appendix). Since most consultancy requests to date were focused on help with the running and hosting of individual instances, we believe de.NBI's scalable OpenStack¹⁸ based Cloud VM approach is a very good fit to host KGs.

5.2.4 WP4 - Community engagement and consultancy (11 PMs UB Mannheim, 3 PMs TIB, 2 PMs ZBW)

This WP will develop and implement a strategic plan for engaging the NFDI community, offering consultancy and training. Serving as a **central contact point** for the KGI services, WP4's activities will focus on **knowledge-sharing and capacity building**. Our **consultancy services** will offer one-on-one or small-group sessions to address specific challenges faced by researchers, consortia, or institutions in their KG projects. The **workshops and training sessions** will be designed and organised to build practical skills for using KGs. **Open educational resources** on KGs, as well as **user-centered documentation** of the KGI services will be published to support adoption and the work of WP3. Knowledge-sharing events such as the **NFDI Knowledge Graph Day, webinars, and hand-on sessions** will be organised to share use cases and stimulate cross-disciplinary collaboration. **Feedback mechanisms** will ensure continuous improvement, including post-event surveys and an online feedback form. Engagement with the NFDI working group "Knowledge Graphs" in Section Metadata will continue through regular meetings to discuss advancements, challenges, and opportunities in the field. A final report will measure **community impact** against defined KPIs, such as the number of workshops conducted, participants engaged, consultancy requests resolved, and the number of educational resources published.

5.2.5 WP5 - Integration and collaboration with other Base Services (14 PMs TIB, 6 PMs FIZ, 2 PMs ZB MED)

This WP will focus on enabling technical integration and collaboration with existing Base Services that can be used within the KGI service or alternatively, that can make use of the KGI service. The work will be split into three phases resulting in three milestones and one key reporting deliverable,

¹⁸ <https://www.openstack.org/>

besides continuing engagement at **Base4NFDI events**. In the first phase, we will engage with services with higher TRLs in their Integration Phase. We envision close cooperation with **TS4NFDI**: Embedding access to TS widgets in the service Hub and Registry will facilitate better data integration as well as easier querying. Additionally, support for the **IAM4NFDI** service will enable personalization features in the Hub, such as saving queries, for example, which will be easily accessible to anyone with an existing NFDI account login. The **Jupyter4NFDI** service also offers exciting opportunities for integration, e.g. by configuring dedicated Jupyter notebooks to query (the Hub) and/or deploy individual KGs. In the second phase of the work, we will consider services that may have lower TRLs, but offer alternative routes for collaboration beyond integration of technical components. With the **RDMTraining4NFDI** service, we can benefit from shared training materials regarding the use, querying and deployment of KGs. The **DMP4NFDI** service provides further resources for users to refer to when it comes to selecting tooling and managing data to be stored in a KG, which can be integrated in our Consulting activities (**WP4**). In the third phase of the work, we will consider new services, e.g. **Accounting4NFDI**, and in principle could be used to cover the whole NFDI services portfolio. Furthermore, through active outreach and participation at events, we hope to explore potential synergies with other **upcoming services** and incubator opportunities that are yet to be announced. A final technical report deliverable will detail use cases, best practices, and links to code repositories for service integrations.

5.2.6 WP6 - Coordination and Outreach (5 PMs ZB MED, 1 PMs GESIS, 1 PM FIZ, 1 PM UB Mannheim, 1 PM ZBW)

This WP will facilitate seamless collaboration among the six funded partners by organizing regular project meetings with a defined agenda covering progress updates, discussion of key issues, and decision-making. Project progress will be monitored by tracking key **KPIs** to assess project effectiveness and identify areas for improvement. This WP will take care of meeting core Base4NFDI service requirements: providing up-to-date **service portfolio metadata**; documenting **service maturity, sustainability and usability** via mid-term and final reporting; in addition to carrying out regular **self-assessments of software quality**. A **Scientific Advisory Board** will be established and meet twice a year in a virtual format to **evaluate project progress, address strategic issues, and make high-level decisions**. We will keep in close exchange with the BASE4NFDI team and engage with other relevant stakeholders, such as other NFDI consortia, relevant research communities and other KG providers (e.g. OpenAIRE and HMC). This will involve developing and implementing a comprehensive **outreach strategy** (together with **WP4**), creating engaging **communication materials** and reaching target audiences through NFDI section meetings and related events, scientific conferences, workshops, online platforms, and social media. While WP4 focuses on deeper engagement and capacity building with service users, this

WP has a more communication-oriented focus towards **reaching new audiences** by sharing project progress and results via diverse communication channels. Dissemination efforts include **publishing findings** in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings, making data and resources openly accessible, and preparing **reports and presentations** for stakeholders and the public. Additionally, it will coordinate the follow-up proposal for the project's Ramping up phase.

6 Funding Request

Funding request of the original proposal were removed in this document.

6.1 Other Funding Sources

We declare that we do not have any other funding sources.

II **Appendix**

A Acknowledgements

This proposal has been supported by the Base4NFDI team as well as the NFDI Section “Metadata, Terminologies, Provenance” by providing valuable advice and guidance for the resubmission process. This section’s “Knowledge Graphs” WG supported the KGI4NFDI basic service by community engagement regarding knowledge graphs within the NFDI.

B Letters of commitment (LoC)

In the following section, we attach the letters of commitments (LoC) supporting the Basic Service development.

Letters of commitment of the original proposal were removed in this document.